

FLUJO GAS-LÍQUIDO EN TUBERÍAS SOBRE TERRENO DESNIVELADO: UN SUMARIO DEL COMPORTAMIENTO FÍSICO Y MODELOS

RESUMEN

El flujo de gas-líquido en líneas de transporte de petróleo y gas sobre terreno desnivelado es un fenómeno muy complejo. Debido a los efectos del terreno desnivelado, los métodos en régimen estable para el cálculo del comportamiento del flujo no son suficientes. Predicciones de ingeniería confiables y métodos de análisis para este tipo de flujo son obligatorios en los proyectos petroleros modernos. Un sumario de las características observadas en campo, estudios experimentales y enfoques de los modelos relacionados con el flujo de gas-líquido en tuberías sobre terreno desnivelado es presentado en este trabajo. Eventos tales como flujo tapón no esperado, mayores caídas de presión y bloqueos de líquido pueden tener lugar durante la operación de una línea de transporte. En la revisión de la literatura se identifican experimentos y modelos teóricos que describen dicho comportamiento. Los modelos incluidos son: balances hidrostáticos dependientes del tiempo con segregación de fases y modelos unidimensionales tanto con el enfoque de mezcla como con el de dos fluidos. Estos modelos son la base de los códigos computacionales comerciales tales como OLGA y TACITE. La información condensada en este trabajo se considera de relevancia para el personal responsable de conducir las operaciones y efectuar análisis del flujo gas-líquido que muestre un comportamiento anómalo asociado con tuberías sobre terreno desnivelado.

Palabras clave: flujo gas-líquido, línea de transporte, modelos matemáticos

GAS-LIQUID FLOW IN HILLY-TERRAIN PIPELINES: A SUMMARY OF PHYSICAL BEHAVIOR AND MODELS

ABSTRACT

The gas-liquid flow in oil and gas transport pipelines over hilly-terrain is a very complex phenomenon. Due to hilly-terrain effects, the steady state methods for calculation of flow behavior are not enough. Reliable engineering prediction and analysis methods of this type of flow are compulsory for modern oilfield projects. A summary of oilfield observed features, experimental studies and modeling approaches related to the gas-liquid flow in hilly-terrain pipelines are presented in this paper. Events like unexpected slug flow, higher pressure drops and liquid blockage might arise during the pipeline operation. Experiments and theoretical models describing this behavior are identified in the literature review. The models included are: time-dependent hydrostatic balances with gravitational segregation, mixture and two-fluid one-dimensional continuum models. These models are the base of well known commercial computer codes such as OLGA and TACITE. The information condensed in this work is considered to be of relevance for personnel responsible to conduct operations and analysis of gas-liquid flow exhibiting the anomalous behavior associated with hilly-terrain pipelines.

Keywords: gas-liquid flow, hilly-terrain, pipeline, mathematical models

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Pipelines transporting oil and gas mixtures are usually laid on hilly-terrain. Pipeline elevation changes might go from small irregularities to large height changes like those encountered in mountainous terrains, seabed and sand dunes. These pipes carry the produced fluids from the wellhead to the primary separation facilities where free gas is removed from the liquid. The multiphase flow in pipes over hilly-terrain exhibits a complex, highly fluctuating behavior. This flow is more difficult to study than the traditional flow in straight pipes, being horizontal, vertical or inclined. A favorable combination of terrain irregularities and flow conditions may lead to the accumulation of liquid at the lower levels of the pipe and pressure build-up. Large liquid slugs can be formed, which will eventually be put in sudden motion by pressure unbalances, thus generating an unsteady multiphase flow.

Two-phase flow in hilly-terrain pipes is important due to its impact on surface processing facilities and, in general, over the whole oil and gas production system. Facilities must be designed to handle large fluctuations of fluid flow produced by the influence of terrain irregularities. Diverse problems may arise such as: a) overflow of gas-liquid separators due to large liquid slugs, b) impaired production from natural flowing and gas-lifted oil wells because of pressure build-up at the wellhead, c) pipeline structural failures caused by the impact of fast, massive liquid slugs, and d) large unexpected pressure drops [1, 2].

Two-phase flow in hilly-terrain has been studied theoretically and experimentally during the previous three decades. An excellent introduction to this subject from an engineering point of view can be found in Shoham [3]. After performing

a literature review of two-phase flow in hilly-terrain pipes and risers, the authors realized that a summary of the relevant information on this subject would be welcome by oilfield engineers and people not familiar with the subject. In this work, a review of the published literature on the subject is performed, summarizing the observed features in experiments, field tests and theoretical modeling. The concepts covered here are at the core of more evolved topics like transient two-phase flow in completely horizontal pipes, flow instabilities, severe slugging in pipeline-riser systems and slug tracking models, each being a subject apart.

FEATURES OBSERVED IN FIELD OPERATIONS AND EXPERIMENTS

Two-phase flow in hilly-terrain pipelines exhibits some remarkable features observable at the macro scale or field operational level. Hints of this anomalous behavior were pointed out since the early eighties [4, 5]. The observed physical behavior of flow in hilly-terrain that distinguishes it from flow in a straight pipe is summarized below.

Unexpected flow pattern. The two-phase flow pattern in any section of a hilly-terrain pipe is likely to be different from the pattern that should exist if the pipe were completely horizontal. For example, the flow pattern present in an upward pipe section might persist in the downward section [6]. The reason for this to happen is that the flow pattern transition due to changes in pipe angle is not instantaneous. Instead, a certain amount of time is required to reach the new equilibrium conditions. If this time is large compared to that required by the fluids to flow through the pipe geometry change, the equilibrium might not be reached at all [7, 8].

Different pressure drops. Pressure gradients could be significantly different in transient hilly-terrain flow than in steady-state flow. If steady-state methods are used to estimate pressure drops, their values might be inaccurate and a departure from the measured values could be important [7]. Steady-state methods may underestimate the pressure drop in the range of 15 to 20% [1].

Terrain slugging. For low liquid velocities, the liquid is prone to pool at the lower sections or valleys of a pipeline [3, 8–10]. This liquid accumulation builds-up until a blockage of the pipe cross sectional area occurs. Thus, a large liquid slug is formed. Sooner or later, this large slug will be put in sudden motion when the hydrostatic pressure between the pipe inlet and the obstruction is large enough. This slug can persist for long distances [1, 7, 10–13]. Moreover, during pipeline transient operation, such as opening and closing of valves, start up and shutdown, large liquid slugs can be accumulated [1, 14]. Other minor events related to the liquid

blockage are oscillations of wellhead back pressure and disturbances of the normal operation of gas-liquid separators [1, 15].

Summaries of experiments in hilly-terrain loops are described in the literature [2, 6, 12, 15–17]. These loops consist of a transparent pipe with usually one or two hills and valleys in order to simulate specific trajectories. Experiments in transient two-phase flow in hilly-terrain are very complex because the diversity in pipe trajectory and flow rates is endless. A results comparison from different sources is not likely to yield any meaningful universal conclusion. Linga [16] says ‘...as terrain slugging is a strongly system dependent phenomenon, the obtained results cannot be extrapolated directly to an arbitrary field transport system. To do that a dynamic two-phase flow simulator is necessary’. Nevertheless, it can be said that experiments reported in the literature have three general objectives: a) reproduce the conditions leading to the observed terrain induced slugging in field pipelines, b) mathematical model testing and c) data generation to further improve said models.

Two broad types of flowing behavior are found in experiments: stable flow and terrain induced slugging [12, 16]. Stable, steady-state flow occurs once the transient flow due to start up has vanished. The transient flow consists of filling up the pipe and further development of stable flow patterns in the uphill and downhill sections. On the other hand, the terrain induced slugging flow exhibits a non-steady, cyclic behavior. Here, liquid accumulates in the valleys of the pipe until it gets expelled out of the system, resembling the same phenomenon already mentioned in the field pipes due to liquid blockage.

MODELS

This section contains a summary of the fluid mechanics modeling techniques that have been applied to transient multiphase flow in hilly-terrain pipelines for crude oil and gas transportation. Another review which includes thermodynamic models and numerical schemes can be found in Lopez & Dhulesia [18]. Two-phase models used for pipes in hilly-terrain are a simplification of rigorous continuum mechanics models, which were written long before the petroleum industry became aware of this type of transient flow. See for example Delhaye [19]. The models included in the present work can be broadly divided into two families, depending upon its core approach: a) quasi-equilibrium models [20–23] and b) two-fluid models [9–11, 24–26].

Quasi-equilibrium models

This approach assumes that there is no need to consider the

time derivative in the momentum equation for transient analysis since the time rate of change in an oil and gas transportation pipeline are rather slow. So, linear steady-state momentum equations are used. On the other hand, mass balance does include the time derivative to take into account variable flow rates along the pipe.

Taitel et al. [20] proposed a model with constant gas flow rate at any cross section of the pipe. The equation $\partial A_l / \partial t + \partial Q_l / \partial x = 0$ is the liquid mass balance, which includes the time derivative for the area occupied by the liquid and it is the only transient equation of the model. The basic statement is completed considering the existence of three flow patterns: stratified, slug and bubble. Momentum equations for each pattern are proposed based on previous mechanistic models, all of them steady-state. Minami & Shoham [22] improved the flow pattern transition criteria to be used in transient conditions. In a later work, Taitel and Barnea [23] introduced a modification on the solution procedure of the basic Taitel et al.'s 1989 [20] model to take into account the variation of gas flow rate.

A model based on a hydrostatic pressure balance and separated phases was written by Taitel et al. [21]. The pipeline is broken down into straight inclined sections following the trajectory of the terrain. A mandatory condition is that no completely horizontal section is allowed. The gas and liquid are fed in a known quantity as a function of time at the pipe inlet. The flow rates are required to be low enough so friction losses can be neglected. The liquid is segregated at the bottom of the pipe and the gas goes up to the top of the pipe. In this way, the whole pipeline may be regarded as chain of U tubes partially filled with liquid. The amount of mass of gas and liquid will be determined by a hydrostatic pressure balance along the system. This model gives rise to a closed set of algebraic equations solved numerically. A stability analysis is performed on each of the flow modes that are possible.

Two-fluid models

In order to understand similarities and differences among the various two-fluid models, a common ground must be laid beforehand. We shall follow a general formulation of Yadigaroglu and Lahey [27]. Consider two fluids, gas and liquid, flowing in a non-specified flow pattern, one-dimensional, time dependent flow, through a duct of any inclination. The continuity equations are:

$$\underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_l \langle \alpha_l \rangle A_p)}_a + \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho_l \langle \alpha_l \rangle \langle v_l \rangle_l A_p)}_b = - \underbrace{\delta w'}_c, \quad (1)$$

$$\underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_g \langle \alpha_g \rangle A_p)}_a + \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho_g \langle \alpha_g \rangle \langle v_g \rangle_g A_p)}_b = - \underbrace{\delta w'}_c. \quad (2)$$

Equation (1) is for liquid and Equation (2) $\delta w'$ is for gas. In Equations. (1) and (2) is the mass rate of liquid change into gas per unit axial length. Quantities in brackets $\langle \rangle$ are averages over the pipe cross sectional defined as follows:

$$\langle \alpha_l \rangle = \frac{1}{A_p} \int_{A_p} \alpha_l dA, \quad (3)$$

$$\langle \alpha_g \rangle = \frac{1}{A_p} \int_{A_p} \alpha_g dA, \quad (4)$$

$$\langle v_l \rangle_l = \frac{1}{A_p \langle \alpha_l \rangle} \int_{A_p} v_l \alpha_l dA, \quad (5)$$

$$\langle v_g \rangle_g = \frac{1}{A_p \langle \alpha_g \rangle} \int_{A_p} v_g \alpha_g dA. \quad (6)$$

Non-steady momentum equations for liquid and gas are respectively:

$$\underbrace{-\langle \alpha_l \rangle \frac{\partial p_l}{\partial z}}_a - \underbrace{g \rho_l \langle \alpha_l \rangle \sin \theta}_b - \underbrace{\frac{\tau_{wl} p_l}{4A_p}}_c + \underbrace{\frac{\tau_l p_l}{A_p}}_d = \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_l \langle \alpha_l \rangle \langle v_l \rangle_l)}_e + \underbrace{\frac{1}{A_p} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho_l A_p \langle \alpha_l v_l^2 \rangle)}_f + \underbrace{\frac{\delta w'}{A_p} (\eta \langle v_l \rangle_l + (1-\eta) \langle v_g \rangle_g)}_g, \quad (7)$$

$$\underbrace{-\langle \alpha_l \rangle \frac{\partial p_g}{\partial z}}_a - \underbrace{g \rho_g \langle \alpha_g \rangle \sin \theta}_b - \underbrace{\frac{\tau_l p_l}{4A_p}}_c + \underbrace{\frac{\tau_{wg} p_g}{A_p}}_d = \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_g \langle \alpha_g \rangle \langle v_g \rangle_g)}_e + \underbrace{\frac{1}{A_p} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho_g A_p \langle \alpha_g v_g^2 \rangle)}_f + \underbrace{\frac{\delta w'}{A_p} (\eta \langle v_l \rangle_l + (1-\eta) \langle v_g \rangle_g)}_g. \quad (8)$$

Term a of Equations . (7) and (8) is the pressure gradient, which is different in the liquid and in the gas for the two-fluid model. Term b is the gravitational pressure gradient. Terms c and d are the frictional forces generated by the presence of solid surfaces and a vapor-liquid interface. Terms e and f are the temporal and convective accelerations.

Term g is the momentum exchange due to evaporation of liquid into gas. The η factor, that seems to be first proposed by Wallis [28], distributes the momentum exchange between phases. The value of η is process dependent. A further simplification of the two-fluid model is the drift-flux model. Here, there is just one momentum equation for a mixture of liquid and gas with the same pressure gradient. Phases are allowed to move at different velocities or drift with a relative velocity.

In the literature, there are some warnings about the mathematical form of Equations . (7) and (8) [3, 20, 29]. Taitel [29] points out that '... there are some basic mathematical problems with this model as the formulation is not always well-posed'. An example of a stable formulation of the two-fluid model is presented by Song & Ishii [30].

A review of some two-fluid and related models available in the open literature is presented below. Since velocities and fluid fractions used in these models are always area averages, brackets are dropped for the sake of simplicity. Focus is done on the mass conservation and momentum equations.

Sarica et al. [10] proposed a model consisting of a combination of the straight inclined sections (see [21]) and a drift-flux model. The flow model in hilly-terrain is an adaptation of the model developed for severe slugging in pipeline-riser systems with low liquid velocity [31]. The problem was split into downward sections and upward sections. For downward flow, there is one ordinary differential equation with respect to time for the gas and another for the liquid. For upward flow, there are mass conservation equations for gas and liquid, and a time dependent hydrostatic balance equation. These three equations are partial differential with respect to time and position along the upward inclined section. Closure relationships are provided to solve the system of equations.

A two-fluid concept for both steady and transient flow is presented by Bendiksen et al. [9]. A set of six partial differential equations with respect to time and position along the pipe are considered. Mass transfer between phases, entrainment and deposition rates and possible mass sources are also taken into account. The model is, in principle, unified for all flow patterns, but in practice, adaptations must be made for each flow pattern using pertinent assumptions. The flow patterns considered are separated flow and distributed flow. Separated flow is further divided into stratified and annular mist. Likewise, distributed flow is disaggregated into bubble and slug flow. This model is the base of the OLGA computer code. Mass conservation and momentum equations are written down for liquid at the wall or bulk liquid, liquid droplets and the gas phase. The liquid (Equation 9), droplets (Equation 10) and gas (Equation 11) mass conservation equations are as follows:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_l \alpha_l A_p) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho_l \alpha_l v_l A_p) - \delta_{w'} \left(\frac{\alpha_l}{\alpha_l + \alpha_d} \right) + \underbrace{(-\psi_e + \psi_d + G_l)}_b A_p, \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_l \alpha_l A_p) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho_l \alpha_l v_l A_p) - \delta_{w'} \left(\frac{\alpha_l}{\alpha_l + \alpha_d} \right) + \underbrace{(-\psi_e + \psi_d + G_l)}_b A_p, \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_g \alpha_g A_p) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho_g \alpha_g v_g A_p) = \underbrace{\delta_{w'}}_a + \underbrace{G_g A_p}_b, \quad (11)$$

$$\alpha_l + \alpha_d + \alpha_g = 1. \quad (12)$$

The model above distributes the liquid mass into two streams,

one for bulk liquid and the other one made up of droplets. Thus, the liquid mass evaporated from the bulk liquid and from the droplets represented by terms a in Equations (9) and (10) is accounted for in term a of Equation (11). Also, there is the possibility of liquid jumping back and forth between the bulk liquid and the droplets stream through the terms b and c of Equations (9) and (10). Finally, liquid can get into the pipe through terms d of Equation (9) and (10) and term b of Equation (11).

The momentum equations are:

$$\begin{aligned} & -\alpha_l \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} - g \rho_l \alpha_l \sin \theta - \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \lambda_l \rho_l |v_r| v_r \left(\frac{P_l}{4A_p} \right)}_a \\ & + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \lambda_l \rho_g |v_r| v_r \left(\frac{P_l}{4A_p} \right)}_b = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_l \alpha_l v_l) + \frac{1}{A_p} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho_l A_p \alpha_l v_l^2) \quad (13) \\ & + \underbrace{\frac{\delta_{w'}}{A_p} \frac{\alpha_l}{\alpha_l + \alpha_d} v_a}_c + \underbrace{\psi_e v_l}_d - \underbrace{\psi_d v_d}_e - \underbrace{\alpha_l D (\rho_l - \rho_g) g \frac{\partial \alpha_l}{\partial z} \cos \theta}_f, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_d \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} - g \rho_l \alpha_d \sin \theta + \underbrace{F}_a & = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_l \alpha_d v_d) + \frac{1}{A_p} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho_l A_p \alpha_d v_d^2) \\ & + \underbrace{\frac{\delta_{w'}}{A_p} \frac{\alpha_d}{\alpha_l + \alpha_d} v_a}_b - \underbrace{\psi_e v_l}_c - \underbrace{\psi_d v_d}_d, \quad (14) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & -\alpha_g \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} - g \rho_g \alpha_g \sin \theta - \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \lambda_g \rho_g |v_g| v_g \left(\frac{P_g}{4A_p} \right)}_a \\ & - \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \lambda_l \rho_g |v_r| v_r \left(\frac{P_l}{4A_p} \right)}_b - \underbrace{F}_c = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_g \alpha_g v_g) + \frac{1}{A_p} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho_g A_p \alpha_g v_g^2) \\ & - \underbrace{\frac{\delta_{w'}}{A_p} v_a}_d. \quad (15) \end{aligned}$$

There is no pressure distinction between phases, so $p_l = p_g = p$. This is a simplification with respect to Equations (7) and (8) where each phase is considered to have different pressure. The shear stress terms c and d of Equations (7) and (8) are present in the form of a friction factor in terms a and b of Equations (13) and (15) where λ_l , λ_g and λ_r are the liquid, gas and interfacial friction factors, respectively. The variable v_r is the relative velocity between gas and liquid calculated as $v_r = R_d (v_l - v_g)$, where R_d is a slip factor. On the other hand, droplets are under the influence of a drag term F resulting from the interaction between gas and droplets by means of term a in Equation (14) and term c in Equation (15). Wall friction factors for gas and liquid and interfacial friction factors are given explicitly by the authors; λ_l and λ_g are those of either laminar or turbulent flow, as if it were pipe flow. Different λ_r formulas are given for annular and stratified flows. Momentum exchange between liquid and gas phases are terms c in Eq. (13), b in Equation (14) and d in Equation (15). Momentum changes derived from the entrainment

and deposition of droplets are taken into account by terms d and e in Equation (13) and terms c and d in Equation (14). Term f in Equation (13) takes into account a hydrostatic driving force due to liquid stratification.

A drift-flux type model for multiphase flow in pipes under steady-state and transient conditions is formulated by Pauchon et al. [24, 25]. The flow patterns are divided into two groups: separated flow (stratified and annular) and dispersed flow. A combination of these two flow patterns is possible, termed intermittent flow (slug and bubble). Four partial differential equations are written: mass conservation for liquid and gas, mixture momentum and mixture energy. Closure relationships are provided depending upon the flow pattern. This model is used by the TACITE software. Liquid and gas conservation Equations are (1) and (2) [24]. Being a drift-flux model, there is only one momentum equation:

$$-\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} - g(\rho_g \alpha_g + \rho_l \alpha_l) \sin \theta + \frac{T^w}{a} - \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_g \alpha_g v_g + \rho_l \alpha_l v_l) - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} - (\rho_g \alpha_g v_g^2 + \rho_l \alpha_l v_l^2) + \frac{\partial M_c}{\partial z} \quad (16)$$

Wall friction forces and interfacial forces are packed together in term a . This term is flow pattern dependent, no further detail is given by the authors. This is equivalent to terms c and d in Equation (7) and (8). Term b is the '... non-homogeneous distribution of void and velocities in the separated and dispersed parts' [24]. This element seems to allow the drift-flux model to better accommodate different flow patterns. Nevertheless, the physics carried by b in Equation (16) is close to term g in Equations (7) and (8) because the variables that build M_c are related to momentum: densities, velocities, phase fractions and flow pattern, though η is absent.

De Henau & Raithby [26] presented a very detailed slug flow, two-fluid model. There are mass and conservation equations for gas and liquid. Proper closure relationships are provided in order to model the slug flow. A virtual mass definition is used to take into account the force needed to accelerate the liquid and to improve the stability of the system of equations. The mass conservation equations do not consider mass exchange between phases. So $\delta w'$ is set equal to zero in Equations (1) and (2). The momentum equations are:

$$-\alpha_l \frac{\partial p_l}{\partial z} - g \rho_l \alpha_l \sin \theta + \frac{\Gamma_{Lw}}{A_p} + \frac{\Gamma_{Li}}{A_p} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_l \alpha_l v_l) + \frac{1}{A_p} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho_l A_p \alpha_l v_l^2), \quad (17)$$

$$-\alpha_g \frac{\partial p_g}{\partial z} - g \rho_g \alpha_g \sin \theta + \frac{\Gamma_{Gw}}{A_p} + \frac{\Gamma_{Gi}}{A_p} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_g \alpha_g v_g) + \frac{1}{A_p} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho_g A_p \alpha_g v_g^2). \quad (18)$$

Terms a and b in Equations (17) and (18) represent the wall and interfacial friction forces. Explicit expressions for

these forces are found using a steady state control volume analysis of slug flow [32]. There is good agreement between experiments and predictions of this model [12].

A summary of the models mentioned before is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of models

Formulation	Reference	Streams	Mass exchange	Flow pattern
Quasi-equilibrium	Taitel et al. [20] Taitel & Barnea [23]	Gas, liquid	No	Stratified, slug, bubble
Time-dependent hydrostatics	Taitel et al. [21]	Gas, liquid	No	Slug flow
	Sarica et al. [10]	Gas, liquid	No	Slug flow
Two-fluid	Bendiksen et al. [9]	Gas, bulk liquid, droplets	Yes	Stratified, annular, bubble, slug flow
	De Henau & Raithby [26]	Gas, liquid	No	Slug flow
Drift-flux	Pauchon et al. [24]	Gas, liquid	Yes	Stratified, annular, dispersed, slug flow

Computer codes

In engineering practice, models are delivered through computer codes. The purpose of commercial codes like TACITE and OLGA is to predict: a) propagation of liquid slugs along the pipe, b) pressure and temperature profiles during transient flow generated by inlet flow rate variations, outlet depressurization, shutdown and restart, pigging operations and c) terrain induced slug flow [13]. Lesser known codes are PeTra [15] and PLAC [11].

OLGA was developed between 1984-1989 by the Institute for Energy Technology, Norway [33] and Sintef. This code has proved its usefulness for the design and analysis of pipelines over hilly-terrain, with good prediction capabilities for pressure drop, slug length and cyclic behavior of the flow. Applications of this code can be found elsewhere [33–35].

TACITE was the product of a cooperation of the Institut Français du Pétrole, Total, Elf Aquitaine, Institut de Mécanique des Fluides de Toulouse and the École Supérieure de Lyon. This code was tested against the Boussens and Sintef loops data [36]. Also, tests against Tulsa University Fluid Flow Project database of transient flow in pipes gave accurate results [25]. Other tests of TACITE and OLGA are presented in [14, 18, 37].

PLAC is a code adapted from the previous TRAC code used in nuclear power generation plants [11]. The PLAC code is intended to describe transient gas-liquid flow in pipes of any inclination angle. The code solves mass conservation and momentum equations for gas and liquid. No details are given about the wall and interface friction factors, but the authors used experimental data to choose them from

available methods. These factors are clearly flow pattern dependent.

There is room for improvements in commercially available software for transient two-phase flow in hilly-terrain regarding pressure drop predictions which might be underestimate [1, 14]. More data is needed to assess the performance of available software [36]. Some problems like smooth pipe inlet pressure increase due to terrain slugging seems to be unsatisfactorily handled and facilities designed with these programs might go undersized [14]. Nevertheless, it is much better to use any of these programs than to employ just steady-state calculations [14, 18]. Recently, a new development of a general multiphase and multifluid simulator called LEDA is proposed [38]. This is a joint effort of ConocoPhillips, Total and Sintef. The developers aim to obtain a code with both, one and three dimensional capabilities.

Computer codes application to field cases

Likewise experimental results, it doesn't look practical to present field experiences regarding hilly-terrain flow in a unified manner. Each pipeline has its own behavior due to its specific trajectory, turning the collected data case specific. Also, field measurements are quite difficult to achieve due to the size of the facilities and that these measurements must be done without (hopefully) disturbing the operations. Thus, a well rounded data collection campaign is usually beyond reach. Nevertheless, from the literature, it is clear that performing field measurements and comparing these results with computer code output is quite useful to understand the behavior of a given pipeline and thus, increase the controllability or improve the design of said pipeline. Some examples follow.

Burke & Kashou [33] acquired data from a 6000 m offshore pipeline in West Africa, with a 15 m level difference from inlet to outlet. Hold-up was measured by means of densitometers close at the pipe outlet. The authors compared calculated slugs characteristics using OLGA with the field measurements, obtaining a very good agreement for pressure drop, average slug liquid hold-up and average slug length values. This analysis was used to properly design slug catchers and surface facilities control systems.

Lopez et al. [18] used TACITE and OLGA to evaluate the behavior of a 41 km long pipeline laid on off-shore hilly-terrain in Indonesia. The output of both computer codes were in agreement with measured output liquid and gas flow rates and inlet pressure in transient conditions, TACITE performing better though. Later, Irfansyah et al. [36] analyzed a slug catcher system pressure fluctuations and flow of water, condensate and gas due to pigging operations associated with this pipeline. Computed results with OLGA matched quite well the measurements, helping operators to better

understand and control the pigging procedures. In Mazzoni et al. [35] can be found another example of transient flow due to pigging operations in Trecate-Villafortuna onshore field. These authors used OLGA for transient analysis and TACITE for steady-state cases. Both codes yielded sound results compared with field measurements.

Alvarez & Al-Awwami [1] performed slug flow tests on a trunk lines system in a Saudi Arabian oilfield. The pipelines are laid on sand dunes that may have heights of 200 m. Measurements of pressure drop and liquid hold-up were taken. The flow was analyzed using OLGA 2000. The pressure drop calculated was about 90% of the measured value. The authors also used a steady-state code, but these results were found to be inadequate for matching the flow conditions. The multiphase flow simulator was used to predict slug flow behavior, pressure drop and performance of surface facilities under varying conditions. Based on these calculations, it was decided to install plug valves near the trunkline outlet to successfully control the flow slugging: 'Choking was found to effectively dampen the severity of the slug effects into the receiving separator by reducing the slug length ...'

Kashou et al. [34] performed several studies of transient flow due to shutdown and restart operations in deep and shallow water pipelines in the North Sea. In these cases, OLGA was used to predict pressure drops and temperatures along the pipes. Of particular interest was the start up procedure once fluids have cooled down inside the pipelines. Results lead to improvements in the hydrate prevention procedures when restarting the pipeline.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

A summary of the relevant features of two-phase flow in hilly-terrain pipelines was presented. The knowledge chain related to this field of production engineering can be depicted as shown in Fig. 1. Acknowledgement of important problems such as liquid accumulation at pipeline low sections, unexpected pressure drops and heavy slugging led to a research and development effort. The outcome materialized in the open literature by means of different modeling approaches. These methods may be classified into two categories: a) quasi-equilibrium and time-dependent hydrostatics and b) one-dimensional continuum models based on mass conservation and linear momentum laws. The latter type of models is split into two-fluid and mixture formulations. The differences among models are contained in flow pattern dependent submodels for wall and gas-liquid interface friction relationships, and mass and momentum exchange between gas and liquid. So, the performance of the different models will depend heavily on these submodels. All these knowledge was made available to the practicing engineers through industrial level computer codes like TACITE, OLGA, etc.

The reviewed literature points out that the use of steady-state analysis for two-phase flow in pipes in hilly-terrain is not enough. It is recommended to do transient flow analysis employing codes specifically designed for this purpose.

The use of computer codes has been proved useful when applied to pressure drop analysis, slug catchers design, pigging operations and plant shutdown and restart.

Fig. 1. Knowledge chain of multiphase flow in hilly-terrain

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NOMENCLATURE

Latin symbols

A_l = area occupied by liquid, m^2
 A_p = pipe cross section area, m^2
 D = pipe diameter, m
 F = droplets drag force, N/m^3
 G = mass flux per unit length, $kg/m^3 s$
 G_d = external droplets source, $kg/m^3 s$
 G_g = external gas source, $kg/m^3 s$
 G_l = external liquid source, $kg/m^3 s$
 g = gravitational acceleration, m/s^2
 M_c = momentum exchange, N/m^3
 P_g = gas wetted perimeter, m
 P_l = liquid wetted perimeter, m
 P_i = interface perimeter, m
 p = pressure in both phases, Pa

p_g = pressure in gas phase, Pa
 p_l = pressure in liquid phase, Pa
 Q_l = liquid flow rate, m^3/s
 R_d = slip factor for gas and liquid velocities
 T^w = stress at wall per unit length, N/m^3
 t = time, s
 V_a = special velocity, m/s
 V_d = droplets velocity, m/s
 V_g = gas velocity, m/s
 V_i = interface velocity, m/s
 V_l = liquid velocity, m/s
 V_r = relative velocity, m/s
 z = axial coordinate, m

Greek symbols

α_d = droplets fraction
 α_g = gas fraction
 α_l = liquid fraction
 $\delta w'$ = phase change, kg/ms
 Γ_{gl} = gas interface friction, N/m
 Γ_{GW} = gas friction at wall, N/m

Γ_{li} = liquid interface friction, N/m
 Γ_{lw} = liquid friction at wall, N/m
 η = fraction of force due to phase change action on gas
 λ_i = gas-liquid interface friction factor
 λ_l = liquid friction factor
 λ_g = gas friction factor
 θ = angle, rad
 ρ_g = gas density, kg/m³
 ρ_l = liquid density, kg/m³
 τ_i = drag stress at interface, N/m²
 τ_{wg} = wall drag stress on the gas, N/m²
 τ_{wl} = wall drag stress on the liquid, N/m²
 ψ_d = droplets deposition, kg/m³ s
 ψ_e = droplets entrainment, kg/m³ s

Other symbols

$\langle \rangle$ = area average

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